

BE-UP: EU-FUNDED PROJECT TO DRIVE INNOVATION IN SUSTAINABLE PACKAGING

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Abstract: *The Be-UP project, funded by the Horizon Europe programme, represents a step forward in the pursuit of a more sustainable future for the packaging industry. By uniting 17 partners from 9 countries, the project's main objective is to accelerate the industrial uptake of biodegradable polymers across Europe. Officially launched on May 1st, 2025, and coordinated by the Spanish technology centre ITENE, the project focuses on developing innovative aliphatic-aromatic biopolyesters with a high content of renewable raw materials, thereby directly contributing to the goals of the European Green Deal. At the core of the Be-UP project is the development of new synthesis and processing methods for biopolymers. This includes the use of bio-based building blocks in combination with advanced catalysts and additives. A key role is played by advanced digital modelling tools, such as the Kinetic Monte Carlo (kMC) method, which enable the optimization of synthesis and polymerization processes. The resulting biopolyesters will be blended with established commercial biopolymers like PLA, PBAT, and PHA, as well as bio-based chain extenders and mineral fillers. Through advanced techniques such as innovative screw design and inline rheology measurements, the Be-UP project will strive to create high-performance bioplastic materials that meet specific technical, sustainability, and biodegradability targets. The project places special emphasis on transferring its results into industrial practice, focusing on key processes in the packaging industry, namely blown film extrusion, injection moulding, and thermoforming. Packaging product prototypes, such as films, containers, and closures, will be manufactured to a Technology Readiness Level of TRL7. These prototypes will serve to validate the developed materials under real-world conditions. A crucial part of the project is the assessment of the materials' biodegradability in various end-of-life scenarios, including open environments and controlled conditions. The findings from these tests will be essential for understanding the materials' behaviour beyond standard laboratory testing. The main expected outcomes of the Be-UP project include guidelines and tools for circular design based on the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework; evidence-based improvements to the regulatory framework for testing and labelling packaging materials; and the development of circular business models for the industrial-scale production of bio-based and biodegradable packaging materials. Ultimately, the Be-UP project will make a concrete contribution to the implementation of several key European strategies and directives, including the Plastics Strategy, the Single-Use Plastics Directive, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation. By developing innovative, sustainable, and competitive solutions, Be-UP is laying the groundwork for a greener and more circular future for the European packaging industry.*

Keywords: biopolyester, PLA, PBAT, PHA, packaging